

CALCULATION OF THE MAGNETISING COIL FOR IMPROVING THE MAGNETIC SEPARATION

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ABSTRACT. A coil intended for magnetisation of finely ground magnetite ores during secondary extraction of iron is considered. It is in the shape of a cylindrical ring and is strung on the pulp tube, which is made of non-magnetic and non-conductive material. The coil has known dimensions of the inner diameter and length, obtained for technological reasons. A direct current with a large alternating current component flows through the coil, formed by a diode half-wave rectifier circuit. A methodology is given for determining the electrical parameters of the winding at a given mains supply voltage, heat load and cooling conditions.

Keywords: magnetising coil, magnetic separation, heat load

Introduction

After magnetisation of the ferromagnetic minerals, which are present in ore pulps, relatively stable aggregates are formed, which are a set of particles with residual magnetisation - magnetic flocs. The magnetic floc behaves as a separate, larger magnetic particle until it breaks down. The problem is that the magnetic flocs are formed quite rapidly in the operational area of the separator due to the abrupt introduction of the material under the influence of a strong magnetic field, which is a prerequisite for trapping the slurry particles inside the flocs.

In order to uncover the finely injected useful mineral particles during the secondary extraction of the magnetic iron from the tailings, it is necessary to grind the material, which is a further complication. During the grinding, secondary slurries of non-magnetic and weakly magnetic minerals are formed, which contaminate the flocs. The particles in the pulp with increased coercive properties make it difficult to destroy the magnetic flocs and the purification technological operations are inefficient.

One way to reduce flocs' contamination is to apply preliminary selective magnetic flocculation in separate magnetisers. Their operation must provide conditions for selectivity with respect to the magnetisation of the particles, in the formation of flocs in the suspension's volume. This is done by gradually increasing the intensity of the magnetic field as the material passes through the operational area of the apparatus. This technological operation must precede the magnetic separation.

Wiring diagram and geometric dimensions of the magnetising coil

A coil of copper conductor is mounted on a non-magnetic and non-conducting pipe, through which a pulp with material subjected to magnetic separation flows (Klisuranov, 1989).

The coil is cylindrical with a rectangular cross section and known dimensions. The inner diameter D_1 , the outer diameter D_2 and the length a are set in advance (Figure 1).

The power supply is also set - one-way rectified waded voltage of 400 V (Alexandrov, Savov, 2018) - linear mains voltage without any power matching transformer (Figure 2).

The aim is to create a pulsating magnetic field with a constant and variable component inside the tube, so that the field intensity is maximum at the maximum permissible heat load of the winding.

Fig. 1. Geometric dimensions of the magnetising coil

Fig. 2. Simplified wiring diagram for the magnetising coil

It is necessary to determine the number of turns W , the inductance L , the cross section of the conductor S_c and the active resistance R , so that the parameters could set the winding in the specified mode.

Defining the inductance L

Under item 6-5 of a specialized guide (Kalantarov, Zeitlin, 1970) a calculation is made for a round winding with a rectangular cross section (Figure 1).

The geometric dimensions of the winding are calculated:
Mean diameter - equation (1):

$$d = \frac{D_1 + D_2}{2} = 264 \text{ mm} \quad (1)$$

Width - equation (2):

$$r = \frac{D_2 - D_1}{2} = 28 \text{ mm} \quad (2)$$

Relation – equation (3):

$$\rho = \frac{r}{d} = 0,106 \quad (3)$$

Relation – equation (4):

$$\alpha = \frac{a}{d} = 1,019 \quad (4)$$

Relation – equation (5):

$$\gamma = \frac{r}{a} = 0,104 \quad (5)$$

According to the proposed methodology (Kalantarov, Zeitlin, 1970) two parallel calculations from different assumptions are chosen for the winding with a rectangular cross-section, which are based on different assumptions.

In order to avoid gross errors, the results of the two calculations are compared. They should give similar results.

The first calculation is based on the inductance of a solenoid according to the expression:

$$L = W^2 \cdot \frac{\pi}{4} \cdot \mu_0 \cdot \frac{d}{\alpha} \cdot (K_\alpha - k) \quad (6)$$

$\mu_0 = 4\pi \cdot 10^{-7}$ H/m - magnetic permeability (absolute)

$K_\alpha = 0.6928$ – a factor which depends on α and is defined according to Kalantarov and Zeitlin (1970) at α as calculated above.

$k = 0.0608$ – takes into account the end effect factor, depends on ρ and γ , and is determined according to Kalantarov and Zeitlin (1970) at ρ and γ as calculated above.

$$L = W^2 \cdot 1.616 \cdot 10^{-7}, H \quad (6')$$

The second calculation is based on the inductance of a flat disk winding according to the expression:

$$L = W^2 \cdot \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \cdot d \cdot \psi \cdot F \quad (7)$$

$\psi = 38.92$ – a factor which depends on ρ and is defined according to Kalantarov and Zeitlin (1970) at ρ as calculated above.

$F = 0.3088$ – takes into account the end effect factor, depends on ρ and γ , and is determined according to Kalantarov and Zeitlin (1970) at ρ and γ as calculated above.

$$L = W^2 \cdot 1.596 \cdot 10^{-7}, H \quad (7')$$

Both calculations give similar results.

The average value of the two calculations (8) is taken into consideration for our further work.

$$L = W^2 \cdot 1.606 \cdot 10^{-7}, H \quad (8)$$

Determination of the impedance modulus

The active resistance R of the winding is determined according to the expression (9):

$$R = \rho \frac{\ell}{S_c} \quad (9)$$

The length of the conductor is

$$\ell = \pi d W \quad (10)$$

The cross section of the conductor S_c is determined by the cross section of the winding, the number of turns and the winding space factor k .

$$S_c = k \frac{r \cdot a}{W} \quad (11)$$

where $r \cdot a$ is the winding's cross section.

Thus, for the active resistance is obtained expression given by (12):

$$R = W^2 \cdot \rho \cdot \frac{\pi \cdot d}{k \cdot r \cdot a} \quad (12)$$

where:

$$\rho = 0,017 \cdot 10^{-6}, \Omega \frac{m^2}{m}$$

$$R = \frac{W^2}{k} \cdot 1,87 \cdot 10^{-6} \Omega \quad (12')$$

It is assumed $k = 0.9$ for a profile conductor with a rectangular cross section.

$$R = W^2 \cdot 2,08 \cdot 10^{-6} \Omega \quad (12'')$$

It is evident that the active resistance R (12'') as well as the inductance L (7') are proportional to the square of the number of turns W^2 .

The inductive resistance X_L is

$$X_L = \omega L \quad (13)$$

$$X_L = W^2 \cdot 314 \cdot 1,606 \cdot 10^{-7} = W^2 \cdot 50,43 \cdot 10^{-6} \Omega \quad (13')$$

φ is determined from the triangle of impedance by

$$\text{tg} \varphi = \frac{X_L}{R} = \frac{W^2 \cdot 50,43 \cdot 10^{-6}}{W^2 \cdot 2,08 \cdot 10^{-6}} = 24,24 \quad (14)$$

$$\varphi = \arctg 24,24 = 87,6^\circ = 1,53 \text{ rad} \quad (15)$$

It does not depend on W .

Reading from tables for the intermediate values of the argument (Kalantarov, Zeitlin 1970) is done by interpolations.

The modulus of impedance is

$$Z = \sqrt{R^2 + X_L^2} \quad (16)$$

$$Z = W^2 \sqrt{(2,08 \cdot 10^{-6})^2 + (50,43 \cdot 10^{-6})^2} = W^2 \cdot 50,47 \cdot 10^{-6} \quad (16')$$

Determining the instantaneous value of the current through the winding

This current consists of a series of pulses, the pulse starting at the moment of opening the diode t_0 and ending at the moment of blocking the diode t_1 . At purely active load $t_1 = T/2$, at active-inductive load $t_1 > T/2$ where T is the grid period.

The current is determined as a transient process with two components (sinusoidal and exponential), as follows from (17):

$$i(t) = i_{\sin} + i_{\exp} \quad (17)$$

$$i_{\sin} = I_m \cdot \sin(\omega t - \varphi); \quad i_{\exp} = A \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \quad (17')$$

The constant A is defined for $t = 0$.

$$i(0) = I_m \cdot \sin(-\varphi) + A = 0, \quad A = I_m \cdot \sin \varphi \quad (18)$$

$$i(t) = I_m \cdot \left[\sin(\omega t - \varphi) + \sin \varphi \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \right] \quad (19)$$

where I_m is maximum value of the current through the winding

$$I_m = \frac{U_m}{Z} = \frac{\sqrt{2} \cdot 400}{W^2 \cdot 50,47 \cdot 10^{-6}} = \frac{1}{W^2} \cdot 11,21 \cdot 10^6 \text{ A} \quad (20)$$

where U_m is the maximum value of the grid voltage.

Let the moment at which the diode is blocked and the current becomes zero be t_1 . Then

$$\sin(\omega t_1 - \varphi) = -\sin \varphi \cdot e^{-\frac{t_1}{\tau}} \quad (21)$$

where

$$\varphi = 87,6^\circ = 1,53 \text{ rad}$$

$$\sin \varphi = 0,999 = 1$$

$$\tau = \frac{L}{R} = \frac{W^2 \cdot 1,606 \cdot 10^{-7}}{W^2 \cdot 2,08 \cdot 10^{-6}} = 0,0772 \quad (22)$$

The time constant τ , does not depend on W .

After substituting the numerical values in (21) for a grid with frequency of 50 Hz, we get:

$$\sin(100\pi t_1 - 1,53) = -e^{-12,95 t_1} \quad (23)$$

The sine function and the exponential function are graphically presented (Figure 3) and their intersection point, which corresponds to t_1 between $0,8T$ and $0,9T$, is determined.

Fig. 3. Graph of current components

For example, for $t_1 = 0,89 \cdot T$ the functions acquire the following values:

$$\sin(100\pi t_1 - 1,53) = -0,796 \quad (24)$$

$$-e^{-12,95 t_1} = -0,794 \quad (25)$$

which are very similar.

It is assumed that the diode is blocked at a time

$$t_1 = 0,89 \cdot T = 0,89 \cdot 0,02 = 0,0178 \text{ s.} \quad (26)$$

Defining the effective value of the current

The effective value of the current can be presented by:

$$I^2 = I_{ac}^2 + I_{dc}^2 \quad (27)$$

$$I^2 = \frac{I_m^2}{T} \int_0^{t_1} \sin^2(\omega t - \varphi) \cdot dt + \frac{I_m^2}{T} \int_0^{t_1} e^{-\frac{2t}{\tau}} \cdot dt \quad (28)$$

The solution of the two defined integrals is:

$$I^2 = \frac{I_m^2}{T} \left[\frac{t}{2} - \frac{1}{4\omega} \cdot \sin(2\omega t - 2\varphi) - \frac{\tau}{2} \cdot e^{-\frac{2t}{\tau}} \right] \Bigg|_0^{t_1} = \frac{I_m^2}{T} \left[\frac{t_1}{2} - \frac{1}{4\omega} \cdot \sin(2\omega t_1 - 2\varphi) + \frac{1}{4\omega} \cdot \sin 2\varphi - \frac{\tau}{2} \cdot e^{-\frac{2t_1}{\tau}} + \frac{\tau}{2} \right] \quad (29)$$

After substituting the above values of (20), (26), (22), $\varphi = 1,53 \text{ rad}$, $\omega = 314 \text{ rad/s}$ and $T = 0,02 \text{ s}$ in (29) we obtain (30):

$$I^2 = I_m^2 \cdot 1,1155 \quad (30)$$

where I – effective value of the current which has a constant and a variable component, I_m – maximum value of the variable component.

Correspondingly, the effective value of the current I , is

$$I = 11,88 \cdot 10^6 / W^2, \text{ A.} \quad (31)$$

Determination of the number of turns W according to the heat load of the winding

Defining the surface of the winding S_{wind}

$$S_{wind} = \pi(D_1 + D_2) \cdot a + 2\pi r dr = \pi(236 + 292) \cdot 269 + 2\pi \cdot 264,28 = 492630 \text{ mm}^2 = 4926 \text{ cm}^2 \quad (32)$$

Defining the active power of the winding P

The active power of the winding P is calculated according to the equation (33) where I – effective current value (31) and R – active resistance of the winding (12''):

$$P = I^2 \cdot R = \left(\frac{11,88 \cdot 10^6}{W^2} \right)^2 \cdot W^2 \cdot 2,08 \cdot 10^{-6} \quad (33)$$

So the surface of the winding is S_{wind} = 4962cm² and the active power is

$$P = \frac{1}{W^2} \cdot 293,6 \cdot 10^6, W \quad (34)$$

The number of turns W should be determined so that the surface of the winding is able to emit this power in the surrounding atmosphere primarily through convection. We calculate how many watts are emitted per square centimetre (σ):

$$\sigma = \frac{P}{S_{wind}} = \frac{293,6 \cdot 10^6}{W^2 \cdot 4926} = \frac{59600}{W^2}, \frac{W}{\text{cm}^2} \quad (34)$$

The convection cooling depends on the air temperature and the air circulation that blows and cools the coil.

The value of σ is determined experimentally by a reduced home-made physical model of the winding so that the surface temperature does not exceed 70 °C at temperature of the air of 20 °C. The following expression is used to define the number of turns obtained by rearranging (34)

$$W = \text{sqr}(59600/\sigma) \quad (36)$$

Experimentally obtained values of σ at the permissible temperature of the winding surface, which are used to determine W are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Number of turns according to cooling conditions

σ, W/cm ²	W, turns	Cooling conditions
0,09	814	At better cooling conditions
0,08	863	
0,07	923	At worse cooling conditions

Defining the cross-section of the conductor

After determining the number of turns for the respective cooling conditions, the cross section of the conductor can be found according to formula (11) to give:

$$S_c = k \frac{r \cdot a}{W} = 0,9 \frac{28 \cdot 269}{W} = \frac{6779}{W}, \text{ mm}^2 \quad (37)$$

Defining the magnetomotive force - m.m.f.

To assess the possibilities for creating a magnetic flux and, accordingly, for the magnetisation of the material in the working volume of the device, the m.m.f. is found by dependence (38).

$$F = W \cdot I, A \quad (38)$$

After substituting the current from (31) in (38) the following is obtained for m.m.f.:

$$F = W \frac{11,88 \cdot 10^6}{W^2} = \frac{11,88 \cdot 10^6}{W}, A \quad (39)$$

For the corresponding number of turns from Table 1 the following values of m.m.f. are obtained.

- At W = 814; S_c = 8.33 mm²; F = 14.6 kA.
- At W = 863; S_c = 7.85 mm²; F = 13.8 kA.
- At W = 923; S_c = 7.34 mm²; F = 12.9 kA.

It is evident that at a greater heat load (β = 0.09; W = 814) m.m.f. is 14.6 kA and at a lesser (β = 0.07; W = 923), m.m.f. is 12.9 kA, values which can create a magnetic field with enough intensity for the magnetisation of the material which is in the range from 32 kA/m to 40 kA/m (Klisuranov, 1989).

Conclusion

The number of turns and the cross-section of the conductor of the magnetising coil are defined so that the induction in the pipe is the maximum at the permissible heat load.

On the basis of the presented calculation, an experimental device with a magnetising coil and a power electronic power supply unit has been designed. The manufactured coil is shown on Figure 4.

Fig. 4. The magnetising coil

References:

Aleksandrov R., Savov N., Ustroystvo za selektivna magnetna flokulatsia, Sbornik s dokladi, Natsionalna nauchno-tehnicheska konferentsia s mezhduнародno uchastie Avtomatizatsia v minnata industria i metalurgiyata, BULKAMK'18, 15-16.11.2018, Sofia, 105-109, (in Bulgarian).

Kalantarov P. L., Zeitlin L. A., 1970. Raschet induktivnostey: Spravochnaya kniga, (in Russian).

Klisuranov G., 1989. Magnitni, elektricheski i spetsialni metodi na obogatyavane, Sofia, (in Bulgarian).